

THE IMPORTANCE OF NATURAL CAPITAL CONSUMPTION IN A SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY

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Abstract.

Because of concern about the environment in different parts of the world, several concepts such as sustainable development and green growth are emerging. This includes different interpretations of the balance between the ecological, social and economic aspects of our society by different sectors. This article examines the concept's dependence on natural resources. It clarifies how sustainable development relates to natural capital efficiency.

Key words.

Sustainable development, economic stability, social stability, environmental sustainability, concept, challenges, growth, interventions, policy achievement of developing countries, natural capital index, sustainable competitiveness, resource efficiency, resource efficiency index, resource consumption.

Introduction. The study of sustainable economy and its impact on sustainable development is one of the important and vital topics for many researchers, especially in recent years. A sustainable economy is a mechanism that primarily leads to the improvement and development of human well-being and the reduction of environmental risks. In terms of environmental benefits, it improves the climate by reducing pollution. It also plays an important role in providing employment and investment opportunities, providing material and human resources and opportunities, which will eliminate poverty and disparity between poverty and social classes, which in turn will benefit future generations by preserving resources to ensure its future. It is a long-term strategy for the national economy to overcome crises and achieve economic recovery, as a sustainable economy strives to provide decent work opportunities for all.

One of the most important goals of a sustainable economy is the need to reform policies and regulations. It has the potential to hinder or facilitate a sustainable economy. Achieving a sustainable economy requires fundamental

changes in the structure and strategies of most companies to achieve sustainable physical and human development.

The study sheds light on important aspects, including the concept of a sustainable economy, its importance, goals and levels, the need to transition to a sustainable economy as an indicator of the impact of the most important sustainable economy on sustainable development, and the most important obstacles to achieving it.

The most important goal of the study is to show the importance of a sustainable economy in sustainable development through the optimal use of energy and resources to achieve prosperity for all and increase the economic level while protecting the environment from pollution.

The United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) defines a sustainable economy as a mechanism for improving human well-being while significantly reducing environmental risks and environmental resource scarcity. Simply put, it's an economy that emphasizes producing less carbon emissions and equipping all social groups with resources. It aims to reduce pollution and carbon emissions by increasing resource efficiency and energy consumption. A sustainable economy also seeks to increase incomes and jobs, which must be driven by public and private investment. These investments should be encouraged and supported by targeted public spending, policy reforms and change regulations. The path of development must preserve and improve natural capital. In fact, its formation is limited when the need arises, because it is a source of public interest, and it is a social issue, especially for the population whose safety and lifestyle depend on nature⁸⁴.

The United Nations Environment Program has defined a sustainable economy as a low-carbon economy that improves human quality of life by reducing environmental risks and uses resources efficiently. It also boosts income growth and creates jobs through public and private investment. Its primary mission is to reduce carbon emissions and pollution, while improving resource and energy efficiency and preventing biodiversity loss. This can only be achieved through policy and legislative reform⁸⁵. Moreover, as some have assumed, the principle of "sustainable economy" is not a substitute for sustainable development. On the contrary, achieving stability is almost entirely based on economic reform. On the

⁸⁴ United N 2011 Towards a green economy: Pathways to sustainable development and poverty eradication - a reference for policymakers, Franc, pp.1-5.

⁸⁵ Khanfar, A. (2014). Environmental economics" green economy. Assiut Journal of Environmental Studies, Egypt, 39, 53-63

other hand, new wealth creation through the "brown economy" model does not address social marginalization and resource depletion, and the Millennium Development Goals are still far from achieving sustainability. Although this may seem like a long-term goal, in order to achieve this goal, we must work to "stabilize" the economy⁸⁶.

Literature review. Scientists connect sustainable growth with a sustainable economy through promising changes in the ecological industry sector. This can be achieved by transforming the final technology of environmental protection into resource-saving methods based on innovation and competitive markets. They pointed to a growing interest in rethinking lifestyles beyond sustainability. At a high level, scientists link sustainable growth and a sustainable economy to the ecological industrial sector by transitioning from environmental protection technologies to resource-saving technologies based on innovation and competitive markets⁸⁷.

An element of the structure of the structure of the financial mechanism is the acquisition of all possible accounts for the provision of quality information. An element of the structure of the structure of the financial mechanism is the acquisition of all possible accounts for the provision of quality information. It is necessary to manage the employees of the company that provides information. At this point, we think it is best to look at the selection of helpers as an element. The storage devices transform the data coming into the legal mechanism and provide useful assistance in obtaining their management. The element of the technological mechanism of selection is qualitative.

According to Pollin, R., Garrett-Peltier, H., Heinz, J., Hendricks, B., "Sustainable growth" refers to a concept that describes a form of economic growth that uses natural resources in a sustainable manner. In fact, this term is increasingly used worldwide to present an alternative concept to classical industrial economic growth, which leads to the phenomenon of a sustainable economy, which is a real phenomenon of development and a concept of environmental security⁸⁸.

Lucretia D. It is true that during economic growth, more resources and energy are consumed and more waste is produced that affects the environment. Ideally, extracting high economic value from limited natural resources should provide

⁸⁶ Bina, O. (2013). The green economy and sustainable development: an uneasy balance?. *Environment and Planning C: Government and Policy*, 31(6), 1023-1047.

⁸⁷ Al-Taai, S. H. H. (2021, June). Green economy and sustainable development. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 779, No. 1, p. 012007). IOP Publishing.

⁸⁸ Robert Pollin, Heidi Garrett-Peltier, James Heintz, and Bracken Hendricks 2014. *Green Growth: A U.S. Program for Controlling Climate Change and Expanding Job Opportunities* Amherst, MA, USA, p. 2.

economic growth significantly higher than national resource utilization rates. They expressed the opinion that resource efficiency is the ability to save costs and introduce new technologies capable of regulating economic processes related to this topic⁸⁹.

It depends on opening up new channels of growth through increased resource efficiency, increased innovation, stimulation of new markets with demand for sustainable technologies, stability due to reduced resource price volatility, and increased efficiency through fewer resource problems⁹⁰. However, even if economic stabilization is clearly desirable, the means to achieve such a transition must be fully understood.

Methodology. Based on the identification of the main areas of natural capital, data series are selected as indicators reflecting the country's sustainable competitiveness based on natural resources (natural capital).

The indicators are analyzed for the most recent data available, as well as their development over time, reflecting the current situation and future prospects relative to the size and population of the country. In addition, indicators that measure the depletion or degradation of natural resources are taken into account. The combination of these indicators reflects the current situation. Natural capital is the building block of a country: the physical environment and climatic conditions, together with the extent of human activity that owns or affects the natural environment. A country's natural capital reflects its ability to sustain its population and economy now and in the future.

Historical, statistical, comparative and systematic methods of analysis, expert evaluation method were used in the research, which allowed the author to solve the tasks.

⁸⁹ Dogaru, L. (2021, January). Green economy and green growth—Opportunities for sustainable development. In Proceedings (Vol. 63, No. 1, p. 70). MDPI.

⁹⁰ OECD 2016 Web brochure: Greening productivity measurement POLICY PERSPECTIVES

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Figure 1. Natural capital and its depletion

Results.

Table 1.

Natural- capital index

No	Countries	Natural capital index
1	Colombia(1)	58.4
2	Brazil(2)	57.6
3	Bhutan(3)	56.3
4	Latvia(4)	55.8
5	Sweden(5)	55.7
6	Finland(6)	55.5
7	Canada(7)	55.3
8	Peru(8)	55.3
9	Kyrgistan	49.1
10	Uzbekistan	37.2

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A nation's natural capital is a given value – it is what it is – that is, there are limits to a person's ability to improve or change the availability of natural capital.

Natural capital is under stress almost everywhere in the world. The wide gap between the lowest (less than 25) and the best (72) reflects the unequal distribution of biodiversity around the world.

The natural capital model includes the essence of the available resources that allow a country to be fully self-sufficient: land, water, climate, biodiversity, food production and power, as well as renewable and non-renewable energy and mineral resources. In addition, the extent of resource depletion or degradation that may threaten future self-sufficiency is taken into account to reflect the full picture of existing natural capital.

Table 2.

Resource efficiency index

No	Countries	Resource efficiency index
1	United Kingdom(1)	63.5
2	Sweden(2)	62.5
3	Costa Rica(3)	61.4
4	Sierra Leone(4)	60.1
5	Switzerland(5)	60.1
6	Ireland(6)	60
7	Denmark(7)	59.9
8	Malawi(8)	59.7
9	Kyrgistan	36.7
10	Uzbekistan	33.5

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Resource intensity and productivity index are both based on per capita. Measurement (intensity) and measurement relative to total economic output, water use per unit of GDP (economic efficiency; resource use per unit of value produced). Countries with low resource consumption - per capita and in dollars - score higher. As a result, resource efficiency can be high in developed and less developed countries.

However, the large share of negative trends across all indicators is more worrying: 49% of all indicators show further deterioration, while only 34% are positive. Given the lack of meaningful policies that protect the remaining biosphere and promote sustainable alternatives, and finally add a cost tag to environmental degradation, we unfortunately have to expect further declines in environmental parameters in the future - which will affect other pillars of sustainability in the future.

The main implications of a high or low resource efficiency score are related to stability and sustained economic growth. If global prices for raw materials and energy rise significantly in the future (as trends and most existing studies suggest),

countries at the bottom will have significantly higher costs and higher levels of efficiency compared to countries with higher and intensity to sustain growth.

Debate. Depletion of the country's natural capital hinders the goals of poverty reduction and sustainable development. Environmental assets such as timber or fisheries and ecosystem services such as water filtration and carbon sequestration are critical to human well-being and provide important economic and social benefits.

The World Bank estimates that the global economy could lose \$2.7 trillion by 2030 if certain ecosystem services (pollination, carbon sequestration and storage, fisheries and timber provision) collapse (compared to business as usual). In low-income countries, GDP may decline by an average of 10% annually, with losses especially high in countries dependent on ecosystem services.

Understanding the value of a country's environmental assets is key to sustainable development and economic growth. With growing environmental concerns and considerations, the question remains how successfully economic development and environmental sustainability can coexist. The separation measure can be used as a tool to assess the compatibility of two goals. Decoupling is defined as "decreasing the amount of resources used to support economic growth and decoupling economic development from environmental degradation."

Gross domestic product (GDP) shows how much monetary income or products a country produces in a year; wealth indicates the value of major national assets and therefore the prospects for maintaining and increasing this income in the long term. GDP and wealth are complementary measures of economic performance, and when evaluated together, provide a more complete picture. By tracking wealth trends, one can see whether GDP growth is achieved by building or maintaining capital assets that are stable over the long term, or by liquidating assets. Wealth should be used in conjunction with GDP to provide a means of monitoring the sustainability of economic development.

Research by the World Bank shows that our material well-being is at risk: unsustainable exploitation of nature, mismanagement and misvaluation of resources that constitute national wealth, and lack of collective action at the local, national and regional levels.

In many countries, GDP is growing at the expense of overall wealth and future prosperity. If not properly informed, citizens may wrongly expect their prosperity to last indefinitely. If today's GDP growth comes at the expense of declining per capita wealth, then prosperity will not be sustainable.

In countries such as Russia, Saudi Arabia, Chile, and Israel, domestic natural resource extraction has helped raise a significant share of revenues. This raises concerns about some countries' dependence on natural resource extraction and their ability to sustain past growth rates in the long term.

Ultimately, the goal is to expand coverage to include other types of natural capital, such as land, soil, freshwater, native forests, or wild fisheries.

At the same time, in Norway and the UK, reductions in natural resource extraction are offset by increased use of other resources (such as labor and manufactured capital) or increased productivity.

The natural capital index has nothing to do with whether the country is developed or not, and its economy, and on the contrary, in many cases, this indicator of developed countries turns out to be much lower, because they have a high level of use of natural resources.

The natural capital index can also be called the scale of opportunities for economic development. A lack of resources usually increases the number of ways out of economic difficulties. An example of this is the Arab countries and the Russian Federation. Their financial stability is entirely thanks to natural resources. Countries that rank high on this indicator are considered to have high potential, and efficiency of use is very important.

Sometimes the resource efficiency index does not cover the whole economy because there are countries with very low resource consumption, whose resource productivity can be better calculated by the total GDP. The countries of Costa Rica, Sierra Leone and Malawi, which made it into the top eight, have a high level of overall efficiency, precisely because of their good indicators of natural resource consumption.

Conclusion. For most policymakers, experts can see sustainable development as the result of integrating environmental issues into everyday thinking, decision-making and accountability processes from different disciplines, such as scientists and social scientists. According to reports, almost all southern African countries have established sustainable development authorities responsible for coordinating sustainable development activities and promoting sound environmental management. However, since the legal basis of most of these bodies is located in the legislation on environmental protection, their work tends to the environment.

One of the main tools used to promote sustainable development is environmental assessment based on global principles, focusing on the environment as an integral part of human well-being.

Sustainable development can be achieved not only through reactive policies, but through a change in the vision of preventive policies that integrates the three areas. There is a need to build institutions and develop policies and strategies that support holistic and integrated approaches.

Ensuring the growth of the economy does not create any obstacles to the development of a sustainable economy; on the contrary, the efficient use of resources maintains moderation and ensures continuity. In particular, rational use of natural resources protects against inappropriate use of natural resources through abuse. Some countries are highly dependent on natural resources, and their economic growth indicators are formed mainly by the consumption of natural resources. It is natural that countries with high environmental impact and high resource consumption will have difficulties in ensuring sustainable growth for many years.

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Natural resources and the efficiency of their use serve to increase the economic potential of the country in every way. Nevertheless, there are a number of other factors that should be taken into account that will lead the economy on the path of continuous development. Effective use of energy resources is one of the most important indicators of efficiency in the use of natural capital.

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